

D2.2 Synthesis Report: Key findings on current state analysis

29.04.2024

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List of abbreviations

HEIs	Higher Education Institutions
ITAP	Institutional Transformation Acceleration Projects
R&D	Research and Development
R&I	Research and Innovation
WP	Work Package

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Contact: Rimante Rusaite, rusaite@uiin.org

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Authors: Despoina Kortessidou, Rimante Rusaite, Dr. Sarah Jaber (UIIN)

Editors: Alexandra Zinovyeva, Fleur Schellekens (UIIN)

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Project Consortium

University Industry Innovation Network BV (UIIN) - Netherlands
TUM International GMBH (TUMInt) - Germany
Momentum Marketing Services Limited (MMS) - Ireland
Instituto Superior Tecnico (IST) - Portugal
Universite De La Reunion (UR) – La Reunion, France
Canarias Universidad Europea De Canarias SL (UEC) – Canary Islands, Spain
Universidade da Madeira (UMa) – Madeira, Portugal
Fachhochschule St. Polten GMBH (STPUAS) - Austria
UC Leuven (UCLL) - Belgium
Magyar Agrar- Es Elettudományi Egyetem (MATE) - Hungary
Universitatea Politehnica Timisoara (UPT) - Romania
Vidzemes Augstskola (ViA) - Latvia

In the project, the university partners are represented by or focus the project work on unique departments across their institutions. Specifically:

- UEC: School of Architecture
- UMa: *Higher School of Technology and Management*.
- STPUAS: team of Service Unit Research and Knowledge Transfer
- UCLL: Business Management and Research & Expertise
- MATE: Institute of Agricultural and Food Economics
- ViA: management team and Faculty of Society and Sciences
- IST: Department of Civil Engineering, Architecture & Environment
- UR: ESIROI engineering school
- UPT: Digital Transformation Institute - ID/IFR and e-Learning Centre

Executive Summary:

Current state across the testing partners

About the project

Led by [University Industry Innovation Network \(UIIN\)](#), the **Entrepreneurial & Innovative Universities Accelerator Program** (Accelerate Future HEI project) will develop and test acceleration services to equip universities with the skills and capacity to drive their institutional transformation towards becoming more entrepreneurial and innovative. The project will apply a comprehensive methodology that builds on the status quo and develops a connected vision and set of activities that provide each institution with a tailored transformation action plan.

How we support universities

Purpose of the report

This report presents the project's first year of research (WP2) and addresses the following question: *"What is the current status of external engagement, entrepreneurship and innovation at each of the nine universities of the Accelerate Future HEI's consortium?"*

The methodology is underpinned by UIIN's Entrepreneurial and Innovative University Framework[®], a research-based conceptual model that encompasses the four main dimensions of an entrepreneurial and innovative university:

- **Entrepreneurial Activities** includes the different degrees of institutional engagement across activities with external stakeholders in education, research, valorisation and commercialisation, and management.
- **Entrepreneurial Mindset** explores entrepreneurial skills, attitudes, and interests across university leadership, professional staff, academics and students that would incentivise and support engagement with external stakeholders
- **Organisational Support** examines the institutional commitment, incentivisation, recognition, and support of the entrepreneurial and/or innovative organisation through tangible support structures and services.
- **Impact and External Ecosystem** explores the university's extended ecosystem, as well as the its role and impact in the ecosystem.

The current state analysis was based on a survey that measured the extent of engagement across the four dimensions of the entrepreneurial and innovative university, providing quantitative and qualitative survey responses of academics and/or researchers, professional staff, students and leadership across the nine university partners.

A snapshot of the key findings of the current state analysis is presented below, across the nine testing HEIs. The key findings are presented across the four dimensions of the UIIN Entrepreneurial and Innovative University Framework[®]: (1) entrepreneurial activities across the university, (2) entrepreneurial mindset, (3) organisational support and (4) impact and external ecosystem.

Colour coding legend:

■ Entrepreneurial Activities

■ Entrepreneurial Mindset

■ Organisational Support

■ Impact and External Ecosystem

01

Project Overview, Aim & Approach

An overview of the project's overarching goals, objectives, methodology and consortium.

Project Overview

The **Entrepreneurial & Innovative Universities Accelerator Program** (Accelerate_FutureHEI; thereafter referred as Accelerate Future HEI) project, under the coordination of [University Industry Innovation Network \(UIIN\)](#), was launched in January 2023 and is funded by the European Commission's Horizon Europe program.

Accelerate Future HEI brings together **twelve European partners** from **eleven countries** to develop and implement acceleration services for institutional transformation.

Main Aim

Accelerate Future HEI aims to **develop and test acceleration services to equip Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) with the skills and capacity to drive their institutional transformation towards becoming more entrepreneurial and innovative.** To do that Accelerate Future HEI will apply a robust, comprehensive methodology that builds on the status quo and develops a connected vision and set of activities that provide each institution with tailored institutional transformation acceleration projects (ITAPs). Participating in this initiative provides the HEIs with a unique opportunity to identify key challenges they are facing and dedicate time and resources to develop solutions through unique ITAPs.

Through this project, the HEIs are not doing this alone, but instead receive personalised and peer-to-peer guidance through access to coaches, thematic working group workshops, training workshops and cohort knowledge exchange events. This allows HEIs to take a close internal look at what they want to achieve while receiving external support and guidance to enable them to implement these changes.

Key Objectives

IDENTIFY

the status quo of each HEI and its ecosystem regarding entrepreneurial and innovative activities.

DEVELOP

test and implement acceleration services that help institutions undertake a transformation roadmap and projects

BUILD

the capacity of the participating HEIs' staff to implement the transformation roadmaps through **a skills development program.**

EVALUATE

the strategies from HEIs supervised by an 'Acceleration Board' of **independent experts.**

GENERATE

policy feedback to the European Commission as well as provide widespread dissemination of the pilot results to other target groups.

Project Consortium

Accelerate Future HEI brings together **twelve European partners** from **eleven countries** to develop and implement acceleration services.

Led by [University Industry Innovation Network \(UIIN\)](#), this ambitious project brings together twelve European partners from eleven countries to develop and implement acceleration services. The project consortium unites international experts on developing and supporting acceleration services, together with two established HEI consortia, one from the EIT HEI initiative (INCORE) and one from the European University Alliance (E³UDRES²) and EIT HEI Initiative (E.I.N.S). UIIN, together with TUM International and Momentum are referred to as *acceleration partners* to design and deliver the acceleration services and support the HEI *testing partners* as they implement their initiatives.

Our consortium represents institutions across Europe, including the Outermost Regions. The diversity of the partners will enable the development of overarching services that can be applied in different contexts and enable the HEIs to impact their regions.

Project Approach: Methodology

The project's methodology is based on a **gap analysis** which involves a **three-phase approach** to understand the context, strategy, goals and status quo of each HEI testing partner and to provide an evidence-based and solid starting point to identifying areas and opportunities for institutional transformation. The research, development and implementation phases are underpinned and supported by training, evaluation, dissemination and other activities across the project duration.

Current State Analysis

WP2 | M1 – M12

Uncovering the goals for institutional transformation.

Where are HEIs now?

The aim of this phase is to (1) clarify the desired future state and goals for institutional transformation and (2) understand the current state of each HEI testing partner and provide an evidence base for entrepreneurial and innovative activities at the partner universities. Specifically, WP2 involves activities of pre-scanning, asset mapping, focus groups, and survey. The survey findings will be explored in depth in this report.

Developing Roadmaps & ITAPs

WP3 | M6-M18

What needs to change to achieve the goals and how will you do it?

Subsequently this phase builds on the current state data to define and design an implementation plan to achieve the desired future state and institutional transformation goals and objectives, with regards to entrepreneurial and innovative activities including the identification of opportunities and challenges to address in acceleration services and coaching activities. This will be done through the roadmap workshops as well as Institutional Transformation Acceleration Projects (ITAPs).

Acceleration services pilot-testing

WP4 | M12 – M48

What will you test and implement?

This phase will support the testing partners in implementing the acceleration services and undertake actions towards institutional change, through a mixture of individual HEI and group-based support. Specifically, HEIs will undergo individual ITAP coaching with experts aligned to their core transformation focus areas, to then work on the implementation of their ITAPs and development of their investment strategy.

Capacity Building & Knowledge Exchange Program

WP5 | M1 – M48

HEIs will be supported with knowledge exchange and learning opportunities across the full duration of the project. In addition to the personalised coaching sessions, and the feedback, peer-to-peer feedback and mentoring guidance, which will be provided throughout *Phase 1* and *Phase 2*, HEIs will have access to dedicated events and workshops, including thematic Cohort Knowledge Exchange Events and Accelerate Training Workshops.

Acceleration Impact – Monitoring & Evaluation

WP6 | M1 – M48

The progress of the ITAPs will be tracked through a dedicated monitoring and evaluation mechanism to evaluate the impact and policy implications.

Communication and Dissemination

WP7 | M1 – M48

A communication and dissemination plan will be developed to share the transformation stories and the project's key learnings to benefit the project's community.

Management, QA & Policy Feedback

WP1 | M1 – M48

Adequate management and quality assurance processes and tools will be developed to deliver on the project's outcomes and inform policy.

Project Approach: Foundational conceptual model

The methodology within this project is based on a combination of research and practice. One of the key models underpinning the methodology is the **UIIN Entrepreneurial and Innovative University Framework[®]** - the framework has been developed over 10 years of research and validated in practice to define the key elements of an entrepreneurial and innovative university, and the challenges and success factors associated with HEI transformation to become more entrepreneurial, innovative and engaged.

UIIN Entrepreneurial and Innovative University Framework[®]

Activities

The extent to which HEIs are innovative and entrepreneurial in their activities across education, research, valorisation and governance. This can include facilitating cooperation with surrounding Research & Innovation (R&I) ecosystem actors across all areas of the HEIs, and supporting the transition to knowledge- and digitally-driven HEIs that include research and innovation outputs in teaching.

Mindset

An understanding of the entrepreneurial and innovative mindset across leadership, academics / researchers, professional / administrative staff, and students. This focuses on fostering entrepreneurial and innovative mindsets, not only across entrepreneurial activities but across all activities to develop and nurture a problem-solving approach.

Organisational Support

The organisational mechanisms required for developing both entrepreneurial activities and mindsets within the HEI. These include: strategy and institutional commitment (e.g. HEI research and innovation strategies); support services and activities (e.g. mechanisms to facilitate collaboration and sharing of knowledge, capacity, infrastructure and resources) and incentives and recognition.

Impact & External Ecosystem

The external partners and supporting mechanisms in place to ensure impact pathways and the role of the HEI within its regional ecosystem. It defines the degree to which the HEIs facilitate collaboration with surrounding R&I ecosystem actors and engages citizens in solving societal challenges.

Main Deliverables

An overview of the main deliverables are outlined below, with the current delivered report highlighted.

Management, QA & Policy Feedback M1 – M48

The plan for how we will ensure we deliver on our outcomes & inform policy

D1.1
DMP M6

D1.2
Initial policy briefing M12

D1.3
Interim policy briefing M30

D1.4
Final policy recommendations report M48

Current State Analysis M1 – M12

Uncovering the goals for institutional transformation. Where are HEIs now?

D2.1
Strategic Vision Statements – M12

D2.2
Synthesis Report – M12

Developing Roadmaps & ITAPs M6-M18

What needs to change to achieve the goals and how will you do it?

D3.1
Roadmaps Analysis report - Draft M12

D3.2
Roadmaps Analysis report - Final M18

Acceleration services pilot-testing M12 – M48

What will you test and implement?

D4.1
Summary report - common ITAP issues M12

D4.2
Case study report- ITAPs and results M48

Capacity Building & Knowledge Exchange Program M1 – M48

The plan for how HEIs gain skills and insights for acceleration & transformation

D5.1
Program overview & delivery plan M12

D5.2
Program delivery progress report & updated plan M30

D5.3
Summary of the learning outcomes M48

Acceleration Impact – Monitoring & Evaluation M1 – M48

We will monitor progress and evaluate impact of ITAPs

D6.1
Monitoring & evaluation plan – M12

D6.2
ITAPs Progress report – M30

D6.3
Final Impact Report

Communication and Dissemination M1 – M48

We plan to share our key learnings so others can benefit

D7.1
Initial Plan M6

D7.2
Updated plan & first dissemination report M12

D7.3
Interim dissemination report M30

D7.4
Final dissemination report M48

02

Current State Analysis: Approach

An overview of the process undertaken to determine the current state of each HEI testing partner.

Current State Analysis: Overview of Approach

Work Package 2 (WP2) Current State Analysis prepares the ground for development and implementation of roadmaps and ITAPs for each individual HEI testing partner.

The **aim of this WP is two-fold**: (1) to refine and articulate the vision and strategies of the testing partners regarding the desired future state of their entrepreneurship and innovation and (2) to understand the current state of each testing partner in terms of their entrepreneurial and innovation-focused activities, mindset, challenges, supporting mechanisms and activities. This is done through employing a multi-method approach of pre-scanning, asset mapping, focus group discussions, and surveys. The data gathered during this WP will provide the baseline for WP3's and WP4's development and implementation of ITAPs to accelerate the transition towards becoming more entrepreneurial and innovative university.

The purpose of this activity was to identify and document the strategies, policies, and resources that can support the acceleration services at each pilot-testing HEI. The findings from this activity have influenced the focus group discussions, development of Strategic Vision Statements, and potential areas of improvement for the ITAP implementation. These statements can be found in the **D2.1 Strategic Vision Statements deliverable**.

The aim of this activity was to bring together internal stakeholders from different parts of the HEI to discuss and envision the desired future state for institutional transformation. Based on pre-scanning and asset-mapping results, participants discussed goals and vision aligned with the pilot-testing HEI transformation agenda and the ambition to become a more entrepreneurial and innovative university. The focus group outcomes were crucial in formulating Strategic Vision Statements for each testing HEI.

The primary research question being addressed through the survey is “What is the current status of external engagement, entrepreneurship and innovation at the university?” Complementing the results from the pre-scanning/asset mapping and focus group discussions results, the survey collected tangible quantitative data to further ground the transformational Roadmaps for each testing HEI. The survey revolved around current state of entrepreneurial and innovative activities of individual testing partners (adapting the UIIN Entrepreneurial University Framework[®]) and was analysed and synthesised by UIIN. A survey report was developed and shared with each testing HEI partner.

Current State Analysis: Scope of Survey

Complementing the results from testing partners' pre-scanning and asset mapping activities, as well as the outcomes of 9 focus group discussions (for the focus group's methodology and outputs, refer to **D2.1**), UIIN developed a survey to understand the current status of external engagement, entrepreneurship, and innovation at each of the universities. Each HEI disseminated the survey among their internal stakeholders.

Survey data collection and analysis

The survey focused on collecting quantitative and qualitative data on the current state of entrepreneurial and innovative activities, perceptions and structures for the individual testing partners to provide a solid base for the definition of the ITAPs. The survey was developed following the UIIN Entrepreneurial and Innovative University Framework[®] (refer p.11). Specifically:

- **Entrepreneurial Activities** showcase the different degrees of institutional engagement across activities with external stakeholders on education, research, valorisation and commercialisation, and governance.
- **Entrepreneurial Mindset** explores respondents' perception of the individual entrepreneurial skills, attitudes, and interests that would incentivise and support engagement with external stakeholders
- **Organisational Support** shows the respondents' perception of the institutional commitment, incentivisation, recognition, and support of entrepreneurial and/or innovative activities through tangible support structures and services.
- **Impact and Ecosystem** presents the respondent's interaction with the university's extended ecosystem, as well as the university's role and impact in the ecosystem.

In addition, respondents were asked about their

personal visions and goals regarding the university's journey as a more entrepreneurial institution. Demographic data was collected on different aspects of the respondents' affiliation with the university.

The original language of the survey was English. Based on different partners' needs the survey was also auto-translated into local languages.

UIIN analysed the survey results and produced individual result reports for each of the nine HEIs. This report contains the results of the aggregated analysis of survey respondents across all nine HEIs.

Across the nine testing partners, the survey was filled out by a total of 764 respondents (**Graph 1**) and on average had a 70% completion rate. As for the distribution of the survey respondents, more than half (53%) were students, followed by academics and/or researchers (32%), professional and/or administrative staff (11%), and faculty and/or university leaders (4%).

Respondents across stakeholder groups

Graph 1. Distribution of survey respondents across the testing partner surveys (N=764).

Current State Analysis: Scope of Survey

Graph 2. Distribution of survey respondents across the testing partner countries (N=764). Acceleration partners (grey) did not participate in the survey.

In terms of geographical distribution (**Graph 2**), over one-third of the respondents are from MATE (with 303 respondents), followed by UPT (with 111 respondents), and UEC (with 98 respondents).

An overview of the respondents per testing partner is presented in **Table 1**.

Partner	Number of respondents	%
IST	27	4%
MATE	303	40%
UCLL	41	5%
UEC	98	13%
Uma	49	6%
UR	45	6%
ViA	80	10%
STPUAS	10	1%
UPT	111	15%

Table 1. Number of respondents per testing partner (N=764).

03

Outcomes: Key findings on the current state

The current state analysis provided an overview of the entrepreneurial activities, mindset, structures and ecosystem across the nine HEI testing partners. This section provides a synthesis of the key findings across the testing partners.

Overview

Entrepreneurial Activities – Current State

Overview of Entrepreneurial Activities

Based on UIIN's Entrepreneurial and Innovative University Framework[®], four groups of activities are identified under the dimension of entrepreneurial activities. These include activities within education, research, valorisation and commercialisation, and management which are outlined in more detail below.

- (1) Education activities** entail the provision of a variety of opportunities by the university, such as collaboration as part of regular education programs, challenge-based learning and delivery of courses or training to external stakeholders. Moreover, under this cluster, universities support their internal stakeholders (i.e., academics, students, professional staff and leadership) to improve their innovative knowledge, skills and actions.
- (2) Research activities** refer to the fostering of innovative and collaborative research practices and projects that create an economic impact and contribute to innovation and entrepreneurship. Such activities include collaborative R&D with industry, mobility initiatives for staff and students, as well as offering consulting services to external stakeholders.
- (3) Valorisation and/or commercialisation activities** include a wide range of external entrepreneurial initiatives that seek to generate social and commercial value from knowledge. Such initiatives are academic and student entrepreneurship endeavours, social entrepreneurship activities, collaborative regional innovation development activities, and the commercialisation of R&D results through licensing or patenting.
- (4) Management activities** entail work carried out collaboratively with internal and external stakeholders on a governance level, including shared resources, shared facilities, and participation on external boards to foster new

perspectives, innovation and entrepreneurship at the university.

Throughout the Accelerate Future HEI's WP2 research phase, **community engagement activities** have been identified as a fifth cluster based on one HEI partner's needs and status quo. Community engagement activities include activism, volunteering, and citizen science projects.

Key findings on current state of entrepreneurial activities across the testing partners

- Consensus among **leadership, professional staff** and **academic survey respondents** is that the main engagement activities revolve around **research** and the least in management activities.
- **Research-Engaged academics** mainly engage with external stakeholders through collaborative R&D projects funded by industry and/or public grants.
- **Education-Engaged academic respondents** primarily do so through (external) collaboration in regular education programs.
- **One out of five academic and researcher respondents have not been involved in entrepreneurial activities.**
- The **extent of engagement** across the nine partner universities, as indicated by both academic and professional staff respondents, is generally **moderate**.
- The **majority of the engaged academic respondents** registered no patents (81%), created no spin-offs (88%) or license deals (93%) based on their research.

In Detail

Entrepreneurial Activities – Current State

Extent of Engagement in Entrepreneurial Activities

To understand the current state of the entrepreneurial activities across the nine testing HEI partners, professional staff and leadership survey respondents were asked on the extent they believe that the university engages with external stakeholders in respect to research, education, valorisation and / or commercialisation and management.

Professional staff and leadership respondents' perception of **their universities engagement with external stakeholders varies from high to medium** (see, Graph 3).

Graph 3. Survey results on the extent of entrepreneurial activities, based on professional staff (*dark pink*; n=49) and leadership (*light pink*; n=31) respondent groups across the 9 testing partners. The likert scale ranges from 1 = “Not at all” to 5 = “To a large extent.”

The findings indicate a consensus across leadership and professional staff respondents that the main engagement activities are focused on research-related activities, e.g. joint R&D

projects, consulting, mobility of staff and students, and public engaged research, followed closely by education-related activities (e.g. curriculum design & delivery, challenge-based learning, lifelong learning). On the other hand, both respondent groups reflect that their institutions **engage to a lesser extent** through **management** and **valorisation and/or commercialisation activities**.

To gain a deeper understanding, academic staff across the nine testing partners were asked to which extent they engage in entrepreneurial and innovative activities (see, Graph 4). Academic survey respondents indicated that they engaged the most across research activities and the least in management ones*. Moreover, one out of four respondents have not been involved in entrepreneurial activities.

Graph 4. Overview of the primary entrepreneurial activities that academics undertake based on academic respondent groups (n=301) across the nine partner HEIs. Respondents could select multiple answers.

* For UPT specifically, one third of their academic respondents are engaged in community engagement activities (not pictured).

Academics were then asked to specify the types of activities they undertake within each of the four groups of activities they had indicated involvement in. This allowed for a more in-depth view on the engagement with different activities by the academic respondents (see, **Graph 5**). Overall, across all listed activities, the respondents **rated their engagement from moderate to low**.

Research-engaged respondents (see, **Graph 5, I**.) **mainly engage with external stakeholders through collaborative R&D projects** on a moderate level, i.e., in projects funded by industry and/or public grants. Education-engaged respondents (see, **Graph 5, II**.) primarily

engage with external stakeholders through **collaboration as part of regular education programs** in curriculum design, mentoring, casework, supervision, university visits and guest lectures.

With regards to valorisation, respondents (see, **Graph 5, III**.) mostly collaborate with external stakeholders via **student entrepreneurship** initiatives, e.g., student created start-ups. Finally, when it comes to management activities (see, **Graph 5, IV**.) respondents (Note: N=12) tend to engage with external stakeholders through industry support activities, such as endowments, sponsorship and scholarships.

Graph 5, I-IV. Survey results on the extent of engagement with external stakeholders as part of I. research, II. education, III. valorisation and IV. management activities by academic and/or researcher survey respondents (Research-engaged academics' N=70, education-engaged ones' N=62, valorisation-engaged ones' N=25 and management-engaged ones' N=12). The likert scale ranges from 1 = "Not at all" to 5 = "To a large extent."

When it comes to the different aspects of engagement activities, the analysis of qualitative responses by academic and professional staff respondent groups (of N=117 and N=31, respectively) showcases an alignment across the testing partner institutions.

More specifically, respondents across eight out of nine institutions perceive that **research is organized in innovative and multidisciplinary ways** in their institutions, and it's often undertaken with international partners and collaborators.

The **multidisciplinary element seems also to be embedded in the educational offerings** across six of the testing partners. Educational programs are also recognized for being delivered with innovative pedagogies and often to international students.

Moreover, respondents across four institutions, **recognize the role of active and engaged leadership**. For instance, respondents reflect on the leadership's commitment to educational activities through the support of open

educational resources, open science and open data, as well to management activities through the inclusion of key external partners into governance structures.

Metrics of entrepreneurial activities

Additionally, academic respondents were asked to indicate the extent of their engagement activities using quantitative metrics (see, **Graph 6**). In the last three years, **majority of academics (94%) indicate that they engaged with at least 1 external stakeholder**, and one third of them with more than five stakeholders.

Moreover, it seems that engaged academics' work receives publicity as almost three quarters (72%) have had more than one appearances in public media.

On the other hand, most of the engaged academics registered no patents (80%), created no spin-offs (89%) or license deals (85%) based on their research across the nine testing partners.

Graph 6. Survey results on the number of the engagement and/or entrepreneurship activities the engaged academic respondents participated, based on their involvement in external engagement over the last 1-3 years (N=112). The marks in red correspond to the mean of each statement's responses.

A similar question, like the one asked to academics, was posed to students to determine the extent of their involvement in entrepreneurial and/or innovative activities during their time at the university. (see, **Graph 7**). **57% of the student survey respondents participated in at least 1 entrepreneurial course or lecture** and at least 53% of them in courses involving challenge-based learning.

Additionally, half of the student respondents, whose answers are presented in **Graph 7** below, participated in at least one placement and internship during their studies (51%) and conducted visits to regional companies (53%).

Conversely, during their studies, around **three quarters** of the respondents **did not self-initiate entrepreneurial projects** (72%) or new start-ups (70%).

Graph 7. Survey results on the number of entrepreneurial and/or innovative activities student survey respondents engaged in, during their time at the university (N=275). The marks in red correspond to the mean of each statement's responses.

Overview

Entrepreneurial Mindset – Current State

Overview of Entrepreneurial Mindset

The entrepreneurial mindset focuses on understanding the attitudes and perceptions towards engagement and entrepreneurship and organisational culture across the universities. In the UIIN Entrepreneurial and Innovative University Framework[®], the mindset of four key internal stakeholders is described, while making clear that there are varied perceptions and nuances to entrepreneurship and innovation across Faculties, and activities are largely driven by motivated individuals. In an entrepreneurial university:

- (1) **Academics and researchers** are encouraged to act innovatively and take an entrepreneurial approach towards research and teaching. Entrepreneurial thinking and acting is embedded throughout their activities.
- (2) **Professional and administrative staff** are service-oriented. They take initiative and proactively support entrepreneurial activities, reduce and navigate bureaucracy and solve issues.
- (3) **Students** have an entrepreneurial mindset. They are driven, bold, take ownership and start new activities. Students are entrepreneurs, own start-ups and behave entrepreneurially.
- (4) **Leadership**, as the university's management provides an innovative vision and supports entrepreneurial practices to foster entrepreneurial thinking and acting, including risk-taking.

In the survey, respondents across the four stakeholder groups were asked to rate themselves and others across different elements of entrepreneurial mindset.

Key findings on current state of entrepreneurial mindset across the testing partners

- The survey analysis across the nine testing partners revealed that **academic, professional staff, leadership, and student** survey respondents perceive their **entrepreneurial mindset as moderate**.
- **Leadership respondents**, followed by academics, perceive themselves to have the **highest level of entrepreneurial mindset** within their institutions.
- **Professional staff** respondents are perceived as the **least entrepreneurial** group by both leadership and academics.
- **Students** consider connecting with **networks, experts and facilitating** contact among students interested in entrepreneurship as the most **valuable institutional support** that could enhance their interest in entrepreneurship and pursuing innovative business ideas.
- **Bachelor or master programs** on entrepreneurship are considered to have slightly **less influence in fostering entrepreneurial thinking and action or starting a business** as perceived by the **student respondents**.

In Detail

Entrepreneurial Mindset – Current State

Perception of different stakeholders' mindset

An entrepreneurial mindset allows academics, professional staff, students and leadership, to collectively shape their institution's culture.

Academics, students, professional staff and leadership across the nine testing partners, were asked to what extent they and their colleagues of possess an entrepreneurial mindset.

The survey analysis, showcased that the degree to which **academics, professional staff, leadership and student survey respondents perceive an entrepreneurial mindset was**

overall rated as moderate (see, Graph 8).

In general, **leadership respondents perceive themselves** and followed by academics as **having the highest level of entrepreneurial mindset**. The group that is rated as the second more entrepreneurial, by all four respondent groups is academics. Moreover, the group that is perceived to be the least entrepreneurial by both leadership and academics is professional staff.

Graph 8. Survey results on the degree to which academics and/or researchers (burgundy; n=160), students (pink; n=227), professional staff (dark pink; n=33) and leadership (light pink; n=29) respondents perceive the entrepreneurial mindset of others in the institution. The Likert scale ranges from 1 = "Not at all" to 5 = "To a large extent."

Enhancement of student entrepreneurial pathways

During the survey conducted across nine testing partner institutions, students were also asked to reflect on university activities and support that could enhance their interest in entrepreneurship and pursuing innovative business ideas (see Graph 9).

While all suggested forms of support were considered important, **students particularly valued their universities for connecting them with networks and experts** who could provide additional connections and support when starting a new business. **Facilitating contact among students interested in creating a**

business was also seen as a supportive activity that could enhance their motivation to pursue entrepreneurial endeavors. Project work focused on entrepreneurship was also perceived as an important factor for fostering entrepreneurial mindset.

It is worth noting that **official bachelor or master programs on entrepreneurship were considered to have slightly less influence** in fostering entrepreneurial thinking and action, or starting a business. Similarly, access to the financial means required to start a new business was also perceived as somewhat less important.

Graph 9. Survey results on indicated activities and supporting services provided by universities that could improve students interest in being more entrepreneurial and starting their business, as reflected by student survey respondents (N=212). The Likert scale ranges from 1 = “Not at all” to 5 = “To a large extent.”

Overview

Organisational Support – Current State

Overview of Entrepreneurial Organisational Support

Entrepreneurial organisational support structures, services and incentives act as the backbone, ensuring ensure that entrepreneurial activities and mindsets are not isolated efforts but are successfully woven into the fabric of the institution, as framed on UIIN's Entrepreneurial and Innovative University Framework[®]. This framework dimension includes (1) a strategic institutional commitment to entrepreneurship and/or innovation, (2) support services and activities, (3) support structures and (4) incentive and recognition mechanisms. All four of them are elaborated more on below.

- (1) **Institutional commitment initiatives** entails the universities' long-term public and strategic commitment to entrepreneurship. Through such initiatives, entrepreneurship and innovation is embedded, documented and evidenced in the mission and vision of the institution.
- (2) **Support structures** consider the universities' established structures supporting, coordinating and enabling access to entrepreneurial and external engagement activities.
- (3) **Support services and activities** include the universities' provided support services and activities to its academics and students to undertake entrepreneurial activities, as well as the ones that facilitate collaboration and knowledge-sharing and create a fertile ground for entrepreneurial and/or innovative activities.
- (4) Finally, **incentives and recognition mechanisms** include the embedded systems within universities that incentivise the leadership, academics, professional staff, leadership and students to drive and support entrepreneurial activities. Such

incentives not only motivate individuals but also institutionalise a culture of innovation.

Together, such organisational mechanisms In the survey, each HEI provided a range of support structures available to staff and respondents rated the level of development and importance of the various structures.

Key findings on current state of organisational support across the testing partners

- Survey respondents highlighted the importance of having **documented missions and visions** for entrepreneurial and innovative activities at the university level.
- Respondents highlighted the significance of **inter-disciplinary research centers for supporting** innovation.
- While deemed important, the partnership offices within universities were seen as **needing improvement in supporting engagement activities**, according to academic and professional staff respondents from various institutions.
- The need for **open spaces fostering informal interaction** to support entrepreneurial activities was emphasized by academic respondents.
- Engaged academics, professional staff and students across the nine testing HEIs recognise as most significant supporting mechanisms, **activities that support students in being more entrepreneurial**, such as events and other opportunities for students to engage in innovation activities and entrepreneurial education offerings.

In Detail

Organisational Support – Current State

Overview of Institutional Commitment

One of the organisational support's aspects that was identified throughout the surveys on the current status of the nine HEI partners, was the institutional commitment to entrepreneurship and/or innovation. Highlighting the perceptions of academic, professional staff and leadership survey respondents is very important to pinpoint existing gaps, and opportunities for further improvement. Below we summarise the 5 most important institutional commitment initiatives per HEI and survey respondent group based on qualitative analysis of the reflections of 98 academic, 29 professional staff and 26 leadership survey respondents across the nine HEIs of the consortium.

1. Documented visions and strategies for entrepreneurial and/or innovative activities

For a holistic support of entrepreneurial activities, a documented mission and vision that embraces entrepreneurial thinking and acting is an important first step to communicate each institution's goal. Across the Accelerate Future HEI consortium the existence of these visionary statements and their translation to university-wide strategies and systems for entrepreneurial and innovation activities were identified as very important initiatives specifically by the academic survey respondents of IST, UCLL, UEC, UMa and UR, professional staff respondents of IST, UEC, UMa and UR, and leadership respondents of IST, UEC, UMa and ViA.

Specifically, the academic respondents from UMa, professional staff respondents at STPUAS, UEC, UMa as well as UEC's leadership respondents find the faculty or department-level strategies for entrepreneurial activities equally important as the university-wide strategies.

As part of the strategic planning of

entrepreneurial activities, academic and leadership survey respondents from IST and UMa find embedding entrepreneurial activities into the performance measurement of academics and professional staff valuable.

2. Leadership dedicated to entrepreneurship, innovation and/or collaboration

Moreover, the survey analysis sheds light on the value of existing top level-management positions for entrepreneurship and/or innovation initiatives development. Across the nine partnering HEIs such a senior management position that **takes ownership of entrepreneurship is seen as highly valuable by the academic survey respondents at MATE, UPT, and UR, the staff respondents at IST, STPUAS and UR, and the leadership respondents at IST, UMa and UPT.**

3. (Non-) financial incentives for entrepreneurial activities

To encourage innovation, it is important to define what needs to be incentivised and what the desired outcomes are. Across the nine HEIs, the provision of financial support to kickstart and further develop the entrepreneurial and innovative projects of students was identified as important by the following survey respondents: academics at UPT and ViA, professional staff at MATE and UPT, and leadership at ViA.

Another incentive for entrepreneurship that was identified as important was the organisation of awards related to innovation, to celebrate the entrepreneurial behaviour of mainly academics and staff, but also students and acknowledge the entrepreneurial successes across the university.

Survey respondents that rate this initiative as a meaningful one across their institutions include: academics at IST and UR, staff at IST, MATE, STPUAS, UPT, as well as ViA's leadership.

4. University-wide culture supporting entrepreneurship and/or innovation

The presence of a culture that supports and encourages entrepreneurial approaches and behaviour can raise awareness among staff and students on the value of entrepreneurial activities. One of the most important ways to cultivate an entrepreneurial cultures, was the presence of academic champions and other positive role models for entrepreneurship and innovation.

These initiatives were identified as the most important ones across their institutions by academics at MATE, UCLL and ViA, staff at MATE at ViA, and leadership survey respondents at MATE.

5. Importance of non-university experience and awareness for entrepreneurial skillsets

The survey analysis showcased that the majority of respondents across the academic, professional staff and leadership groups have more years of experience working in universities, than working outside the university sector or being involved in university-industry engagement projects.

However, it was identified that prior experience working in industry should play a stronger role in the requirement of academic and professional staff. Specifically, prior experience outside the university for academics has been pinpointed as important by academic survey respondents at UCLL and UEC, whereas prior experience for professional staff has been identified as important by academics at UEC, staff at ViA and leadership respondents at MATE.

Moreover, a higher awareness among staff would allow for the necessary actions to

establish support systems for students to develop a range of entrepreneurial skills. This was supported by the following survey respondent groups: academics at MATE and ViA, professional staff at UEC and UPT, and leadership at MATE.

Overview of Support Structures

Through the survey, engaged academics and professional staff across the nine partnering HEIs were asked to indicate and rate their **university's internal structures** supporting entrepreneurial and/or innovative initiatives. Below we summarise the five most important support structures per HEI and survey respondent group based on qualitative analysis of the reflections of 94 academic and 34 professional staff survey respondents across the nine testing partners.

1. Inter-disciplinary research centres

Throughout the focus group sessions with the nine partnering HEIs, the topic of supporting innovation to propel HEIs towards becoming active actors of research and innovation within their ecosystem was deemed as very important.

Through the analysis of the survey results, it was identified by academic survey respondents across ViA and professional staff across MATE, UEC, UPT and ViA that inter-disciplinary research centres and researchers of entrepreneurship and innovation are very important in the support of innovative activities.

Moreover, academic respondents at MATE and UR reflect that research facilities could be shared with external stakeholders, such as research-intensive industry actors.

2. Designated offices for partnerships

The survey identified that although academic respondents across the IST, MATE, UEC, UMa, and UPT, and professional staff from UEC and MATE, and find the partnerships office within the university important, it could support engagement activities on a higher degree.

3. Designated offices and teams for knowledge and/or technology transfer activities

In addition to the need for a more supportive partnerships office, academic survey respondents from IST and UPT and professional staff from IST, STPUAS and ViA shared the importance and need knowledge and/or technology transfer offices to provide more support for entrepreneurial initiatives.

Currently, also, academic and professional staff survey respondents from IST, MATE, STPUAS, UR and ViA universities find the designated teams of professional staff that can support knowledge and technology transfer activities very important.

4. Informal spaces at universities to organise entrepreneurship activities

Throughout the focus groups the need for designing bustling open spaces that allow for informal interaction was raised. Spaces like that are seen as important as they enable the serendipitous and semi-structured interaction between academics, students and external stakeholders. This can be a strong catalyst for developing entrepreneurial activities and enable the community and external stakeholders to meet, network, exchange ideas, and understand the industry needs. Through the survey this support structure was rated as particularly important by academic survey respondents across UEC and UR, as well as professional staff respondents at MATE, STPUAS and UCLL.

5. Entrepreneurship associations and/or centres

Apart from establishing informal spaces and opportunities for entrepreneurial creative development, a high number of internal stakeholders identified the importance of formal entrepreneurship associations and/or centres at their institutions to create and facilitate an entrepreneurial environment for students and employees.

Specifically, academic survey respondents from UEC and UMa, and professional staff respondents from UCLL, UEC and UPT find the existence of such support across their institutions very important in supporting entrepreneurial and/or innovative activities.

Overview of Support Services and Activities

Through the survey, engaged academics, professional staff and students across the nine partnering HEIs were asked to indicate the degree to which they consider different mechanisms and services supporting innovation and utilisation of knowledge developed across their institutions. Below we summarise the three most important support structures per HEI and survey respondent group based on qualitative analysis of the reflections of 94 academic, 29 professional staff and 200 student survey respondents across the nine testing partners.

1. Events and other opportunities for students to engage in innovation activities

A supporting mechanism that was perceived to be one of the most developed across the nine testing partners were the entrepreneurship or innovation events and opportunities for students, such as hackathons and social innovation projects, respectively, rated as such by all surveyed engaged academics, i.e., across IST, MATE, UCLL, UEC, UMa, UPT, UR and ViA, and professional staff from seven out of the eight surveyed institutions, i.e., IST, STPUAS, UEC, UMa, UPT, UR and ViA.

Nonetheless, when students across all universities were asked on their universities' most important internal structures in supporting engagement activities, only the student survey respondents from MATE rated events like career days as such, in co most relevant supporting mechanisms for them.

2. Curricular—bound and extra-curricular education offerings for students

Academic and professional staff reflect that students should be provided with access to both curricular-bound courses in entrepreneurship, innovation and the entrepreneurial mindset, as well as stand-alone,

extra-curricular courses and seminars. The survey respondents that rate curricular-bound and extra-curricular courses as important include academics from eight out of nine institutions, i.e., IST, MATE, UCLL, UEC, UMa, UPT, UR and ViA, and professional staff at STPUAS, UEC, UMa, UR and ViA.

Academic and professional staff's perception on the importance of additional entrepreneurial educational offerings for students is aligned with the students' perception on the mechanisms and structures supporting their entrepreneurial activities. Students across seven HEIs, i.e., IST, UCLL, UEC, UMa, UPT, UR and ViA, identified entrepreneurship courses offered across all faculties, entrepreneurship bachelor or masters programs as very important, as well as innovation programs for students and business trial labs.

3. Networks and entrepreneurial events for academics and professional staff

Survey respondents indicated they value opportunities to engage with external stakeholders through knowledge sharing events and networks. These supporting mechanisms are enhanced by the existing support of dedicated business coaches and consultants for academics, as well as information sessions and forums on external engagement specifically offered to staff. These initiatives have been identified as the most important ones across their universities by academic survey respondents at IST and professional staff at IST, MATE, UMa, UPT and ViA.

Most student respondents (across IST, MATE, UCLL, UEC, UPT, UR) also appreciate the opportunity to network and broaden their connections in the field, through student networks and hubs, student entrepreneurship clubs and student organisations representing the educational and social interests of students at the university.

Overview of Incentives and Rewards for Entrepreneurial Activities

Through the survey, engaged academics and professional staff across the nine partnering HEIs were asked to rate the different motivators and incentives that drive external engagement and entrepreneurial activities. Below we summarise the most important incentives for recognising and rewarding entrepreneurial activities of academic and professional staff survey respondents across the nine HEIs of the consortium.

In general, academics have stronger motivation to undertake entrepreneurial and external engagement activities than professional staff (see, **Graph 10**).

Academic respondents tend to be mostly incentivised by their personal willingness, but also because it allows improving the content and

delivery of their courses and applying their research in practice.

Professional staff are also motivated by their personal willingness to engage in entrepreneurial and/or innovative activities, as well as by the contribution to the mission of the university.

In contrast, for both stakeholders, undertaking entrepreneurial activities is not driven by factors such to increase their chances for promotion, and to provide them with recognition .

Graph 10. Survey results on the degree to which academic (burgundy; n = 106) and professional staff (dark pink; n = 32) survey respondents are incentivised to undertake entrepreneurial and/or external engagement activities. The Likert scale ranges from 1 = “Not at all” to 5 = “To a large extent.”

Overview

Impact & External Ecosystem – Current State

Overview of Impact and External Ecosystem

Universities' external ecosystems enable knowledge institutions to commit to translating and disseminating knowledge and build towards a socially sustainable future, while positioning itself as an instrumental actor in the innovation ecosystem. As elaborated in the UIIN Entrepreneurial and Innovative University Framework[®], the universities' external ecosystem aspect examines (1) external support mechanisms, (2) role within their ecosystem, (3) monitoring and evaluation and (4) impact measurement. The survey focused on the first three aspects, specifically:

- (1) **External partners and external supporting mechanisms** include the ways universities collaborate with external partners and are aware of and connected to external supporting mechanisms such as incubators, entrepreneurship centres and venture capital.
- (2) **Role within the ecosystem** studies the different roles of HEIs within their local or regional ecosystem. In this role, universities are aware of their key stakeholders and the (inter)national partners they cater.
- (3) **Monitoring and evaluation** pinpoints the tools and strategies that institutions employ to enhance their capacities for innovation and community involvement, as they strive to stay relevant and responsive to the evolving needs of their staff and students.

Together, such mechanisms ensure that universities fulfil their social impact through the creation of more knowledge-based approaches in their local environment and their region, through the support of entrepreneurial activities and an innovative culture, while being connected to grand global challenges.

Key findings on current state of impact and external ecosystem across the testing partners

- **Leadership survey respondents** across nine testing partners perceive that the **most developed aspect of their universities' role** in the ecosystem is **their contribution as an engine for regional development**.
- Across the nine testing partners, there is a perception of a **strong commitment to collaboration and knowledge exchange** with industry, the public sector, and society across the universities, however, the ability to attract industry to regions based on research strengths is perceived as less developed.
- The **professional staff and leadership respondents** indicate that in general **universities have not adequately developed instruments for continuous improvement**.
- An **exception is the survey instruments** used to measure student satisfaction with education, which are considered to be developed to a medium degree. However, **instruments assessing student satisfaction with entrepreneurial education are in need of improvement**.

Overview of External Supporting Mechanisms

For universities to connect more with outside organisations and their regional and (inter)national ecosystem, external supporting mechanisms are of paramount importance. Through the survey, professional staff and leadership respondents across the nine testing partners were asked to think about the ecosystem surrounding their university, and consider the degree to which they consider the offered external supporting mechanisms as important. Below we summarise the three most important external supporting structures per HEI and survey respondent group based on qualitative analysis of the reflections of 25 professional staff and 23 leadership survey respondents across the seven HEIs of the consortium (survey data from UMa and UCLL were not considered due to insufficient responses).

1. Regional incubation and development agencies

Overall, a large number of the survey respondents shared their view on the importance of regional incubation and development agencies that support student and academic entrepreneurial projects, as well as the greater local communities. Such supporting mechanisms include regional technology transfer offices, (pre-)incubators, entrepreneurship hubs and chambers of commerce, among others.

These initiatives were identified as the most important ones across their institutions by professional staff across all seven surveyed institutions, i.e., IST, MATE, STPUAS, UEC, UPT, UR, and ViA, as well as leadership respondents at IST, UPT and ViA.

2. Mentoring and education programs to support entrepreneurship projects

External supporting mechanisms can provide the financial means, infrastructure, mentoring and education programs or societies for ideas to grow and helps connect entrepreneurs with funding opportunities through a unique set of programs built around entrepreneurship, and/or innovation.

Those who indicated these initiatives as important are professional staff respondents at IST and UEC, as well as leadership respondents at IST, MATE, UEC and UPT.

3. Multidisciplinary research and development spaces

For universities that value research-focused innovation, developing external supporting mechanisms for innovative inter- and multidisciplinary research and practice initiatives is reflected as positive by their internal stakeholders. Living labs and interdisciplinary research centres have been identified as important for external collaborations by professional staff survey respondents at MATE, as well as leadership survey ones at IST, MATE, UEC and ViA.

Overview of Role in the Ecosystem

Universities can adopt many roles to become collaborative, interactive institutions integrated within their local and regional society and ecosystem. To identify the universities' role in the ecosystem as an entrepreneurial and innovative university, the responses of 23 professionals in senior management and faculty leadership positions across the nine testing partners were analysed (see, **Graph 11**).

Leadership survey respondents perceive as the most developed aspect of their universities' role within the ecosystem the degree to which their university is an engine for regional development.

Following, the commitment to collaboration and knowledge exchange with industry, the public sector and society is also developed across the universities.

The respondents indicate that somewhat less developed roles of the universities within their ecosystem include the ability with which universities attract industry to their regions based on their research strengths as well as the linkage with innovation districts, science parks and other external structures.

Overview of Instruments for Continuous improvement

Through the survey analysis on the universities' current state a range of strengths, but also areas for improvement, were identified. Ideally, the identification of developed and effective instruments for continuous improvement can outline tools that can benefit from further

iterations and improvement to better assess and capture the impact metrics across the testing partners' institutions (see, **Graph 12**).

Overall, the professional staff and leadership respondents indicated that the university has not adequately developed the presented instruments for continuous improvement.

One exception is the survey instruments measuring student satisfaction with education which is seen as medium developed by leadership across the nine HEIs.

Based on the respondents' perception the instruments that could benefit from further improvement are the survey instruments in place to assess student satisfaction with their entrepreneurial education and the key performance indicators for entrepreneurial and innovative activities on a faculty or department level.

Graph 11. Survey results on the degree to which leadership survey respondents perceive the universities' role in the ecosystem as an entrepreneurial and innovative university (N=23). The Likert scale ranges from 1 = "Not at all" to 5 = "To a large extent."

Based on the respondents' perception the instruments that could benefit from further improvement are the survey instruments in place to assess student satisfaction with their entrepreneurial education and the key

performance indicators for entrepreneurial and innovative activities on a faculty or department level.

Graph 12. Survey results on the degree to which professional staff (dark pink; n=20) and leadership (light pink; n=16) survey respondents reflect on the contribution of instruments to their universities' continuous improvement as an entrepreneurial and engaged universities. The Likert scale ranges from 1 = "Not at all" to 5 = "To a large extent."

04

Reflection and next steps

Reflecting on the process and next steps

Reflection & next steps

The first phase of the project, WP2 Current State Analysis has established a strong foundation for the testing partners' transformative journey towards becoming more entrepreneurial and innovative.

The insights gained from the **pre-scanning** and **asset mapping** activities have been crucial in documenting the strategies, policies, and resources available to our testing partners at the current state, as well as helping identify their existing strengths and resources.

Furthermore, the participatory nature of the **Desired Future State Focus Group** (refer to **D2.1** for more information) discussions has fostered collaboration among diverse stakeholders within the testing partners' universities. Establishing this collaborative framework, which may have initially seemed challenging, has been instrumental in creating a shared vision for the desired future state (more about the Strategic Vision Statements are presented in **D2.1**). The subsequent focus group reports have raised awareness about the project's activities and set the stage for institutional transformations aimed at nurturing a culture of entrepreneurship and innovation. Participants expressed the importance of having the space and time to undertake these discussions, and have them captured in documents that they can use for further institutional planning.

Finally, the **survey, which effectively addressed the key question regarding the current status of**

entrepreneurial activities, mindset, organisational support and ecosystem of each testing partner, provided evidence-based data. The qualitative insights from focus groups and tangible quantitative data from surveys have laid a comprehensive foundation for the Roadmap Workshops and will further guide the development of ITAPs for each testing HEI.

The current state analysis has laid a solid foundation for the next phase of implementation. With a better understanding of both the current landscape and future aspirations, the testing partners are ready to define and embark on the implementation of ITAPs, directly addressing the identified challenges. The achievements this phase not only mark a significant milestone in the project's trajectory but also play a key role in validating the chosen methodology for developing and testing acceleration services.

Follow our journey

To learn more, visit the project www.acceleratefuturehei.eu

Contact Us

Rimante Rusaite
 Senior Project Officer- UIIN
 E-mail: rusaite@uiin.org
 Web: <https://www.uiin.org/>

